

QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal – User Manual (v0.2.1)

1. Introduction

The **QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal** is a web platform for exploring, exporting, and (for in-kind contributors) curating an AGN catalogue.

The portal supports four user categories:

- **Citizen Scientists** – lightweight access after login (currently limited; future citizen-science tasks planned).
- **Scientists** – full access to scientific search, visualisation, and export tools.
- **In-kind Leads** – scientists (or admins) with additional permissions for data upload/validation workflows.
- **Administrators** – full control over users, roles, and data workflows.

This document explains:

- How to access the portal and request the appropriate role.
 - What each role can see and do.
 - How to search, visualise, and export catalogue data.
 - How in-kind leads and admins manage data and users.
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2. Access & Authentication

2.1 Public landing page

The landing page is public and serves as a presentation layer:

- Short description of the catalogue and science goals.
- Overview of available tools (search, visualisation, exports).
- Terms of use and data policy.
- Button for **Log in**

No login is required to read basic information.

2.2 Logging in

Users can log in via:

- **Google account (OAuth)**
- **ORCID** (OAuth Public)

On first successful login, the system creates an internal user account and assigns the default role:

- **Citizen Scientist** (*internally: `pending_scientist`*)

2.3 Terms of Use screen (first login and updates)

After your first successful login (and whenever the Terms are updated), you will be redirected to a short **Terms of Use** confirmation page:

- Links to the full **Terms of Use** and **Privacy Notice**
- A required confirmation checkbox before continuing

After accepting the Terms, **first-time users** are directed to an additional **Role Selection / Access Choice** screen, where they explicitly choose one of the following:

- **Citizen Science access** (default, for public exploration)
- **Scientist access (LSST DP1 rights required)** — reserved for users with approved LSST DP1 permissions

This step ensures users consciously confirm their intended access level. Once the Terms are accepted for a given version, the Terms screen will not appear again unless the Terms change.

3. Roles and Permissions

3.1 Role model

The system uses **three roles** and **one additional flag/status**:

Role / Flag	Description
Citizen Scientist (<code>pending_scientist</code>)	Default role after first login. Currently limited access; future citizen-science features planned.
Scientist	Full scientific user: advanced search, visualisation, exports, profile & history.
In-kind lead (<i>special status</i>)	A Scientist additionally designated for in-kind workflows (e.g., listed in <code>inkind_leads</code>). Can upload/validate and send accepted batches to staging.
Admin	Full administrative control over users, roles, and data workflows (including final approvals).

Note on terminology: “In-kind lead” is not a separate base role in the UI sense; it is a **Scientist with additional permissions**.

3.2 Citizen Scientist

Assigned on first login (or selected on the Role Selection screen after accepting the Terms).

Current state:

- Citizen Science access is currently **limited** while the public-release policy and the public subset of the catalogue are being finalized.
- Users may see only minimal UI elements intended for general orientation (e.g., landing/dashboard guidance), but **do not have access to the scientific catalogue data** at this time.

Planned capabilities (subject to data-release policy):

- Access to a **restricted public subset** of the catalogue (e.g., selected fields, limited rows, or aggregated views).
- Participation in future citizen-science tasks (e.g., classifications, quality flags, candidate vetting workflows).

Limitations (current):

- Cannot browse or query the full catalogue.
- Cannot run advanced searches.
- Cannot export data (CSV/VOTable/TOPCAT/pyVO).

Note: Availability and scope of Citizen Science access will evolve with future releases and data-rights constraints.

3.3 Scientist

Scientists have access to the full science toolset:

- **QhX – Search** (catalogue browsing + advanced filtering)
- **Visualisation**
- **Exports:**
 - CSV / VOTable downloads

- TOPCAT URL export
- pyVO SCS token and endpoint access
- **Profile page** with basic user info and search/export history

Promotion from Citizen Scientist → Scientist is handled by Admins (see Section 9).

3.4 In-kind Lead (Scientist with in-kind permissions)

An in-kind lead is a Scientist who has been granted additional rights for data contribution workflows.

Capabilities include:

- Upload prepared data files (catalogue extensions / updates)
 - Run validation checks
 - Review validation results
 - Send accepted data into **staging** tables (requires admin approval for promotion to main tables)
 - Optional: Upload auxiliary science products linked to catalogue objects
 - Upload **static images** of:
 - **light curve previews** (per object and/or per band),
 - **spectrum window previews** (where applicable),
 - other agreed QA/diagnostic plots.
 - Each upload must be **linked to a specific `object_id`** (and optionally `band` / metadata).
 - Files are stored as **attachments** and become visible in the object view **only after validation and (if required) admin approval**.
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3.5 Admin

Admins have the broadest permissions:

- All Scientist and In-kind lead capabilities
 - User & role management:
 - Approve / reject scientist access requests
 - Promote Citizen Scientist → Scientist
 - Assign / revoke in-kind lead permissions
 - View which users currently have in-kind status
 - Block users if necessary (abuse/security)
 - Oversight of in-kind workflows:
 - Review uploads + validation reports
 - Approve or reject in-kind batches
 - **Promote approved data from staging tables to the official catalogue tables (e.g., `agn_objects_z`)**
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4. Portal Navigation & Dashboard (Scientist / In-kind Lead)

4.1 Header navigation (top menu)

After login, the portal header provides the primary navigation:

- **Dashboard** – landing page after login, with quick-access buttons.
- **Visualize** – 2D / 3D visualisation tools and plots.

- **Catalogue** – browsing the full catalogue (paginated view).
- **Search Data** – advanced search page (filters such as period range and cone search).
- **Inkind Lead Page** – visible only to users with **in-kind lead permissions** (and Admins). Provides upload/validation workflows.

On the right side of the header:

- A **profile dropdown** (user name + role label) provides access to account-related actions (e.g., profile/logout).

4.2 Dashboard (quick start)

The **Dashboard** page contains shortcut buttons to the most common actions:

- **Visualize data** → opens **Visualize**
- **Browse catalogue** → opens **Catalogue**
- **Search Data** → opens **Search Data**
- **TOPCAT URL generator** → opens the TOPCAT export URL page (tokenised VOTable URL)
- **pyVo URL generator** → opens the pyVO export/token page (programmatic access)
- **Inkind Lead Page** → opens the in-kind workflow page (*only shown if you have in-kind lead permissions*)
- **Features** → opens a page with additional, project-specific tools and prototypes that are not part of the standard LSST/IVOA workflow. These features may be experimental, may change over time, and are intended for internal testing, demonstrations, or extended exploration beyond the core catalogue functions.
- **Raw Outputs with False Discovery Rate `fdr_pass`** → opens a page that provides access to the raw QhX inference outputs for sources that pass the selected False Discovery Rate threshold (`fdr_pass`). This view is intended for internal QA, validation, and in-kind analysis (e.g., inspecting periods, uncertainties, significance metrics, and consistency flags) rather than for general catalogue browsing.

The dashboard may also display:

- current **role badges** (e.g., *scientist*, *in-kind lead*)
- system status (e.g., **online**) and a “last updated” timestamp.

Figure 1. Scientist Dashboard: quick access to catalogue tools, exports, and visualisations.

5. Catalogue Access (Browse & Search)

Both **Catalogue** (Browse) and **Search Data** provide access to the same underlying catalogue tables and share a common workflow:

- view results in a paginated table,
- open an **Object details** page by clicking an object ID,
- export results as **CSV** or **VOTable**.

5.1 Catalogue (Browse)

The **Catalogue (Browse)** page is designed for quick exploration and lightweight filtering:

- Displays a **paginated table** of catalogue objects.
- Provides a fast search/filter input (**q**) for simple lookups (e.g., partial **object ID**).
- Supports additional quick filters for common exploration needs, such as:
 - **verdict / bucket** filtering
 - **period range** filters (e.g., *minP / maxP*) where available

This page is intended for **interactive scanning** of the dataset without building complex multi-parameter queries.

Use this page when:

- you want to quickly browse and scan objects,
- you need a lightweight lookup (e.g., by object identifier),
- you want simple quality/exploration filters (e.g., verdict/bucket),
- you do not need a full cone search or complex numeric constraints (use **Search Data** for that).

QhX Catalogue Showing 10 of 230 objects

Search ID or label Verdict... Bucket... Min period Max period Filter

Export CSV (objects) Export VOTable (objects) Export CSV (objects + bands) Export VOTable (objects + bands) Visualise Data

Object ID	RA (catalog)	DEC (catalog)	Best Period	Period Error (Lower)	Period Error (Upper)	Period Error (Symmetric)	Period Error Source	Observed Baseline (t_obs)	SNR	Period Error Note	Verdict	Bucket
2.496285			2.496285	0.499257	0.499257	0.499257	bad_json	32	0.240000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.24	discarded	red_noise
2.854715			2.854715	0.570943	0.570943	0.570943	bad_json	32	0.220000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.22	discarded	red_noise
3.169811			3.169811	0.633962	0.633962	0.633962	bad_json	32	0.220000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.22	discarded	red_noise
3.290891			3.290891	0.658178	0.658178	0.658178	bad_json	32	0.190000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.19	discarded	red_noise
2.425993			2.425993	0.485199	0.485199	0.485199	bad_json	32	0.190000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.19	discarded	red_noise
3.057325			3.057325	0.611465	0.611465	0.611465	bad_json	32	0.180000	Tobs=32.0d,SNR=0.18	discarded	red_noise

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 ... 23

Figure 2. Catalogue (Browse) page.

5.2 Search Data (Advanced filters)

The **Search Data** page supports targeted queries with **advanced constraints**, including:

- **Period range** filtering (minimum / maximum period in days)
- **Cone search** (RA, Dec + search radius)

Depending on your role and permissions, additional numeric constraints may be available for refining the result set.

Use this page when:

- you need a cone search around a specific sky position,
- you want to constrain results using **numeric ranges** (e.g., period limits),
- you want a well-defined subset of objects for further analysis or export.

TOPCAT shortcut:

Search Data includes a shortcut to **TOPCAT Export**. When used, it opens the TOPCAT URL

generator with the **current filters pre-filled**, so you can immediately generate a VOTable link for TOPCAT.

Figure 3. Search Data: targeted queries using numeric constraints and cone search (RA/Dec + radius)

5.3 Results table (shared behaviour)

Both **Catalogue (Browse)** and **Search Data** display results as a **paginated table** showing the available information for each object.

The table presents a **combined view** of object-related data sourced from the core catalogue tables: **object identity/coordinates**, **core inference outputs (objects_z)**, **multi-band photometry (bands)**, and **mass-related properties** (where available).

Each row represents a single catalogue object, and clicking the **object ID** opens the detailed object view.

5.4 Object details page

Clicking an **object ID** opens the **Object details** page, which consolidates all available information for that object, including:

- object-level parameters,
- band-level metrics (if available),
- links to related data products (if enabled),
- optional attachments (e.g., light curve/spectrum previews) where provided by in-kind workflows.

The Object details page can be reached from both **Catalogue** and **Search Data**.

5.5 Basic exports (CSV / VOTable)

Both **Catalogue** and **Search Data** provide quick exports for the current result set:

- **CSV export**
- **VOTable export**

Exports reflect the **current filter state** on the page and are intended for use in external tools (Python/R/TOPCAT, etc.).

6. Data Visualisation

The **Visualise** section provides interactive tools for exploring the catalogue before exporting to external software. It includes:

- a unified **Visualisations** page for interactive **2D and 3D** plots,
- a separate **Aladin Sky Viewer** page for sky-projection exploration,
- optional project-specific interactive demos (e.g., **sonification**) intended for outreach, internal testing, or extended exploration.

6.1 Visualisations (2D + 3D plots)

The **Visualisations** page offers interactive plots for fast inspection and exploratory analysis. Depending on the selected configuration, you can visualise:

- **Sky distributions** (e.g., RA/Dec in 2D; or RA/Dec with an additional depth axis in 3D where available)
- **Parameter relations** (e.g., period vs SNR, quality metrics, or other available fields)
- **Trend/outlier exploration** using scatter-style views, with optional colour-mapping

These plots are intended for rapid exploration and QA-style checks prior to deeper analysis in external tools.

Controls (Visualisations)

Typical controls include:

- **Mode** selection (2D / 3D)
- **Axis selectors** (choose X / Y and optionally Z)
- **Color by** (map a selected parameter to point colour; numeric colourbars and/or categorical colouring depending on the field)
- **Scale options** (linear/log where applicable)
- Standard interactive navigation (pan/zoom; rotate in 3D; hover tooltips)

Note: The exact set of available fields depends on the current dataset view and your role/permissions.

Figure 4. Visualisations: interactive 3D sky view using magnitude as the colour scale.

6.2 Interactive sky viewer (Aladin)

The portal includes a dedicated **Aladin**-based sky viewer page that can display catalogue objects on an interactive sky projection.

Typical use:

- visually inspect object distribution on the sky,
- confirm cone-search targets and neighbourhoods,

- explore clustering patterns in a presentation-friendly way.

Aladin complements the core catalogue browse/search and export tools.

6.3 QhX Sky Walk — Hear the Bands (Sonification)

The portal also includes a project-specific **sonification** demo that transforms selected multi-band properties into sound for intuitive exploration and outreach.

Typical use:

- explore how objects differ across bands through auditory cues,
- “walk” through objects (e.g., by a chosen ordering) and compare patterns quickly,
- support demonstrations and extended exploration beyond standard LSST/VO workflows.

Disclaimer: Sonification is intended for **demonstration/outreach and exploratory inspection**; it is not a detection claim.

Figure 5. QhX Sky Walk — Hear the Bands: sonification controls (pitch/loudness mapping) and playback interface.

6.4 Project-specific and experimental visual tools (scope note)

Some visualisation widgets (e.g., Aladin integration and sonification demos) are project-specific and may evolve over time. Core catalogue access and reproducible analysis remain available through **Catalogue**, **Search Data**, and standard export mechanisms (**CSV/VOTable**, **TOPCAT**, **pyVO**).

7. Data Export Workflows

Scientists (and Admins / In-kind leads) can export data in several ways.

7.1 Direct export from QhX – Search

After running a search, export buttons above the results table provide:

- **CSV (objects)** – one row per object
- **VOTable (objects)** – VO-compatible format
- **CSV (objects + bands)** – one row per (object, band), includes object- and band-level metrics
- **VOTable (objects + bands)** – VO-compatible format

Use these for quick local analysis (Python/R/TOPCAT, etc.).

7.2 TOPCAT Export URL

The TOPCAT Export page builds a short-lived, tokenised URL.

7.2.1 Steps:

1. Open **TOPCAT Export**
2. (Optional) set filters:
 - Object ID substring

- Min/Max period
 - RA/Dec/Radius
 - Band (G/R/I/Z)
3. To export the full catalogue, check **Include entire dataset (no filters)**
 4. Click **Generate TOPCAT URL**

The page displays a URL you can copy or open in a new tab (returns a VOTable).

7.2.2 In TOPCAT:

- File → Load Table → **URL**
- Paste the URL and confirm

Notes:

- URL is time-limited (e.g. ~15 minutes)
 - Intended for interactive use, not long-term automation
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7.3 pyVO SCS (Simple Cone Search)

For scripted/programmatic access from Python, use the **pyVO Access Data** page (SCS field picker + token generator).

7.3.1 Steps

1. Open **pyVO Access Data**.
2. Select the fields you want returned in the SCS response (checkbox list).
 - You can also use a **preset** (e.g., *core / full*) if available.
3. Enter your cone-search parameters:

- **RA, DEC**
- **SR_ARCSEC** (search radius in arcseconds)
- Optional: **MAXREC** (maximum number of returned rows)
- Optional: **BAND** (limits band-joined output for performance, if supported)

4. Click **Generate**.

The page provides:

- the SCS endpoint URL: [.../vo/conesearch_all_data.php](#)
- a **24h JWT token** (scope: [export:scs](#))
- a **Quick test URL**
- a ready-to-copy **pyVO example**

7.3.2 Example (pyVO)

```
import pyvo

svc = pyvo.dal.SCSService("../vo/conesearch_all_data.php")

token = "PASTE_YOUR_TOKEN_HERE"

q = svc.create_query()

q["RA"] = 53.136324

q["DEC"] = -27.906397

q["SR_ARCSEC"] = "300" # arcseconds

q["MAXREC"] = "50"

q["token"] = token

q["FIELDS"] = "obj_id,ra,dec"

print("PYVO URL:", q.queryurl)

tbl = q.execute().to_table()

print("Rows:", len(tbl))

print(tbl[:5])
```

7.3.3 Returned data

The returned table includes exactly the fields you selected in the **field picker** (or the chosen preset). This typically includes core object identifiers and coordinates, and may include inference outputs (e.g., periods / quality metrics), band-related fields, and mass-related properties where available.

Use this for reproducible notebooks, scripts, and pipelines.

QhX QhX Hub Dashboard Visualize Catalogue Search Data **Inkind Lead Page** Milena Stankovic Cerovic scientist

QhX – Access Data with pyVO

Pick the columns you want (by table), then generate a 24h JWT and a copy/paste pyVO query.

- Choose where to search (Cone Search parameters)**
You can keep the sample values or paste your own coordinates.

RA (deg)	DEC (deg)	SR_ARCSEC	MAXREC
53.136324	-27.906397	300	50
- Pick columns**
Base fields `obj_id`, `ra`, `dec` are always included.

Search columns:

Bands (optional performance helper): DEBUG

If you set `BAND=g`, the query can be lighter (less join rows). Leave empty to allow multiple bands.

Selected fields: `obj_id` `ra` `dec` Clear

Tip: picking too many columns (especially band metrics across all bands) can create very large URLs. Start small, then expand.

Objects Core All

 - Best Period `days`
`obj_best_period`
 - Period Error (Lower) `days`
`obj_per_err_lo`
 - Period Error (Upper) `days`
`obj_per_err_up`
 - Period Error (Symmetric) `days`
`obj_per_err_sym`
 - Period Error Source
`obj_per_err_source`
 - Observed Baseline (t_obs) `days`
`_observed_baseline`

These map to `obj_*` aliases in the full endpoint.

Coordinates Core All

 - RA (catalog) `deg`
`coord_ra_1`
 - DEC (catalog) `deg`
`coord_dec_1`

These map to `coord_*` aliases.

Mass Core All

 - Redshift (Mass table)
`mass_z`
 - Absolute Magnitude (Mi) `mag`
`mass_mi`
 - log(MBH) Median `dex`
`mass_logMBH_med`
 - log(MBH) 16th Percentile `dex`
`mass_logMBH_1o16`
 - log(MBH) 84th Percentile `dex`
`mass_logMBH_hi84`
 - Timescale τ (Median) `days`
`_timescale_tau`

These map to `mass_*` aliases.

Bands (Wide pivot)
Pick which bands and which metrics. We will generate aliases like `g_flux_mean_r_amp_mag`.

Bands

 - u
 - g
 - r
 - i
 - z
 - y

If `BAND=i` is set above, selecting multiple bands may not make sense.

Band metrics All metrics None

<input type="checkbox"/> Period <code>days</code> <code>period_days</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Amplitude <code>mag</code> <code>amp_mag</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Phase <code>cycles</code> <code>phase_cycles</code>
<input type="checkbox"/> Points Used <code>n_points_used</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Median Photometric Error <code>mag</code> <code>median_err</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Amplitude SNR <code>amp_snr</code>
<input type="checkbox"/> R ² <code>r2</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Reference Band <code>ref_band</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Reference Phase <code>cycles</code> <code>ref_phase</code>
<input type="checkbox"/> Phase Lag vs Ref <code>cycles</code> <code>phase_lag_vs_ref</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Good Band <code>good_band</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Coherent Band <code>coherent_band</code>
<input type="checkbox"/> best_period <code>best_period</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Period Error (Lower) <code>days</code> <code>per_err_lo</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Period Error (Upper) <code>days</code> <code>per_err_up</code>
<input type="checkbox"/> Period Error (Symmetric) <code>days</code> <code>per_err_sym</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Verdict <code>verdict</code>	<input type="checkbox"/> Non-reliable Type <code>bucket</code>

Generated aliases will be `<band>_<metric>`. Example: `g_amp_mag`.
- Generate token + copy/paste code**
This creates a token and prints a ready pyVO snippet.

Generate token + example Endpoint: `https://[redacted]/vo/conesearch_all_data.php`
Base columns always included: `obj_id, ra, dec`

SCS Endpoint `[redacted]/vo/conesearch_all_data.php` Copy

JWT Token (24h) `[redacted]` Copy

Quick test URL `[redacted]` Copy

pyVO example (copy/paste)
`import pyvo` Copy

Figure 6. pyVO Access Data: field selection and a ready-to-copy pyVO query example.

8. In-kind Data Upload & Validation (In-kind Leads & Admins)

Note: This section describes the current in-kind ingestion workflow. Details may evolve as the upload module is refined.

8.1 Roles and scope

- **Scientist** can use standard catalogue tools (search, VO export, profile/history). Scientists who are not authorised for in-kind work do not see in-kind upload/lead tools.
- **In-kind lead / in-kind scientist** is a Scientist with explicit in-kind capability. This is treated as an additional authorisation flag rather than a separate standalone role.
- **Admin** has full portal privileges, can access all in-kind batches, and can always perform promotion and rejection actions.

8.2 Upload & validation workflow

8.2.1 Step 1 — Upload + initial validation (In-kind lead)

In the web UI, the in-kind lead uploads **exactly three Parquet files**:

- **coordinates**
- **objects_z** (object-level metrics)
- **bands** (per-band metrics)

Before accepting the upload, the system performs **initial validation**:

- required files are present,
- file types are recognised,
- files can be opened as Parquet,
- expected columns are present,

- **basic value sanity checks pass** (e.g. RA/Dec within valid ranges; required fields non-null; key categorical values within allowed lists).

If initial validation passes, the files are stored and a new **batch** is registered (the batch appears as **Validated** in the UI).

8.2.2 Step 2 — Cross-file `object_id` consistency check (“Ready for staging” check)

After the upload is registered, the in-kind lead runs a **consistency check** to confirm the batch is structurally usable for staging.

This check verifies that:

- **objects_z and coordinates contain the same set of object_id values** (i.e. for every object in the batch, both object-level metrics and coordinates are present),
- **bands is allowed to be a subset**: it may contain fewer objects than objects_z/coordinates (some objects may have no band rows),
- **but bands must not reference unknown objects**: every `object_id` appearing in bands must exist in the objects_z/coordinates set for that batch.

Outcome:

- If the check fails, the batch is marked as **not ready for staging** (an error summary is recorded) and the user should upload a corrected batch.
 - If it passes, the batch becomes **Ready for staging** and the UI exposes “**Import to staging**”.
-

8.2.3 Step 3 — Send to staging (In-kind lead)

“Send to staging” writes the batch data into the staging tables for:

- object-level data,
- coordinates,

- per-band metrics,

tagging all staged rows with the corresponding **batch_id**.

On success, the batch is marked **Staged**, with row counts and **staged_at** recorded.

8.2.4 Step 4 — Import to main catalogue (Admin)

An Admin runs “**Import to main**”, which inserts/updates data from staging into the official catalogue tables as a controlled database operation, and records a detailed entry in the promotion audit log.

On success, the batch becomes **Imported** and **imported_at** is set.

8.2.5 Rejection (Admin)

At any point after upload, a batch can be marked **Rejected**, recording **rejected_at** and a **rejected_reason**. Rejected batches remain in the audit trail but are not used for staging/import.

8.3 Batch status summary (conceptual)

Uploaded → **Validated / validation_failed** → **Ready for staging** → **Staged** → **Imported**
(Reject is possible from most states.)

9. Admin Tools

Admins have access to an additional **Admin** section used for user and role management, monitoring, and in-kind batch approvals.

9.1 User management

Admins can:

- view all registered users and their account details,
- see the current role/status:
 - **Citizen Scientist** (default/entry role),
 - **Scientist**,
 - **Admin**,
- see whether a user has **in-kind lead capability** (authorised in-kind contributor),
- review and process **scientist access requests** (approve / reject),
- promote or demote roles (e.g. **Citizen Scientist** ↔ **Scientist**) according to internal policy,
- grant or revoke **Admin** privileges (according to internal policy),
- grant or revoke **in-kind lead** permissions,
- block or restrict accounts if required (abuse/security).

9.2 Usage statistics and audit

Admins can access basic usage metrics and audit logs, such as:

- search activity (e.g. number of searches, common filter usage such as period range and cone search),
- export activity (e.g. TOPCAT VOTable exports, pyVO/SCS queries),
- token and export audit trails (where enabled by the portal configuration).

These metrics support:

- monitoring system load and operational health,

- reporting on in-kind activity and platform usage,
- understanding how catalogue tools are used by authorised users.

9.3 In-kind batch approval and promotion

For in-kind uploads, Admins can:

- view all upload batches and their statuses (Uploaded / Validated / Ready for staging / Staged / Imported / Rejected),
- review validation results and error summaries (and logs where available),
- perform **final approval** by importing staged data into the official catalogue tables (“Import to main”),
- reject batches and record a rejection reason when needed.